

What are the Prescription Limits of Potentially Inappropriate Medications (PIMs) stated on EU-7 PIM list in Central and Eastern European countries?

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BACKGROUND

- Nowadays, one of the main public health concerns is the appropriate prescribing for older patients (1). According to the study of Oliver Reich et al. the adverse outcome observed as **acute hospitalizations were documented in 25.5 % of individuals using PIMs (potentially inappropriate medications) compared to 18.7 % of non-users (p<0.001)** (2).
- For clinical practice, **different implicit and explicit tools (eg. EU-7 PIM list) (1) have been developed to evaluate appropriate prescribing in older patients. However, still a lot effort must be done at the regulatory level in order to improve the situation in geriatric drug prescribing.**
- Based on previous findings we may expect that **particularly in Central and Eastern Europe the prevalence of PIM use in very high and regulatory measures regarding PIMs availability for prescription widely differ across Europe** (3).

THE AIM OF STUDY

- to investigate what prescription limits are established for EU-7 PIMs in Central and Eastern European countries

METHODOLOGY

Research teams of WG1b EU COST Action IS1402 group (2015-2018) from the

- Czech Republic(CZ),
- Estonia(EST),
- Poland(POL),
- Slovak Republic(SR) and
- Croatia(CR)

Data was collected on approval rates and availability of EU-7 PIMs on prescription or as OTC medications.

Further, data on prescription limits of EU-7 PIMs for different medical specialties was collected from databases of national drug regulatory institutes between July 2017-December 2018 and re-checked between June-August 2019.

Descriptive analyses using SPSS software had been applied to express specificity of EU(7)-PIM list and approval rates of different PIMs in different countries.

RESULTS

- 98.37 % of EU-7 PIMs were available on prescription in Croatia (CR)**, 95.1 % in the Czech Republic (CZ), 91.0 % in the Slovak Republic (SR), 90.6 % in Poland (POL) and 89.9 % in Estonia (EST)
- OTC availability was confirmed for 18.18 % of PIMs in EST**, 15.8 % in POL, 12.5 % in CZ, 12.19 % in CR and 11.9 % in SR
- 35 EU-7 PIMs were available only in one country** (2- CR, 3-CZ, 3-EST, 2- SR and 24-POL, respectively). From active substances these were mainly (in all countries): acetylsalicylic acid, bisacodyl, diclofenac, loperamide and ranitidine.
- The percentages of PIMs available in the reimbursement list (from PIMs approved) were: 96.2 % SR**, 93.5 % CZ, 90.2 % CR, 68 % EST, 40.3 % POL.
- Specialists' prescription limits (for PIMs available in the reimbursement list, R-SP) were established for 48.8 % PIMs in SR**, 34 % in CZ, 29.4 % in EST and 20.7 % in CR. The only country without specialist's prescription limits for PIMs was POL.
- The only PIM that had specialist' prescription limits established for nonreimbursed prescriptions (NR-SP) was methadon in CR.** In all other countries, there were no specialists' prescription limits for nonreimbursed prescriptions for PIMs.

CONCLUSIONS

- In order to reduce problems associated with PIM prescribing in geriatric patients, **it's necessary to establish appropriate regulatory measures and to increase training of medical doctors and pharmacists in problems of PIM use.**
- Replacement of actual PIMs available in the reimbursement list with safer options must be considered and followed with a pharmacoeconomic analysis.
- Prescription limits for PIMs should be harmonized** across Europe.

Graph 1: PIMs from EU-7 list approved for use on prescription or as OTC drugs

Graph 2: Percentages of PIMs approved for the use on the pharmaceutical market in each participating country and PIMs approved in solid p.o drug forms (EU-7 PIM list)

Graph 3: Information related to PIMs and their specialists' prescription limits when they are and they are not part of the reimbursement list (R-SP and NR-SP, respectively)

Graph 4: Specialists prescription limits when PIMs are and are not part of the drug reimbursement list

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